

MICROMECHANICS FOR CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES VIA FIBER SUB-STRUCTURING

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SUMMARY: A methodology combining composite micromechanics with a unique fiber substructuring concept is described. In this new concept, the conventional unit cell (the smallest representative volume element) of the composite is modified by substructuring it into several slices and developing the micromechanics-based equations at the slice level. This methodology has several advantages and allows for a more accurate micromechanical representation of the various constituents of the composite. Although, applicable to different types of composite materials, it is particularly well-suited to simulate the ceramic matrix composites (CMC's) behavior. Important features of this approach and its effectiveness are described by using select examples for a SiC/RBSN composite system. Comparison of predictions and limited experimental data are also provided.

KEYWORDS: micromechanics, unit cell, interphase, interface, progressive fracture, progressive debonding, partial interphase bond, stress redistribution

INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been growing interest in the use of fiber reinforced composite materials in widely varying applications such as aerospace, civil infrastructure, sporting goods, marine applications, automobiles etc. Fiber reinforced composites offer many advantages over traditional materials in higher stiffness/weight ratio, flexibility in design capabilities, excellent corrosion/wear/impact resistance and fatigue strength. The characterization of these materials is fundamental to their reliable use. The analysis of fiber reinforced composites presents many modeling challenges due to heterogeneity of these materials. Unlike their homogeneous isotropic counterparts, the anisotropic construction of laminated composites results in many unique phenomena that occur at different geometrical scales - at the global (laminate) level, the lamina (ply) level as well as at the fiber-matrix (constituent) level. To account for these phenomenon in a more accurate manner, a unique micromechanics based fiber sub-structuring technique has been developed. Although, the technique is applicable to any kind of composite material behavior simulation, it is particularly well suited for simulating aspects unique to ceramic matrix composite behavior. The design of interphase/coating plays a key role in ceramic matrix composites to enhance their fracture toughness. It is well known that ceramic matrix composites are reinforced primarily to enhance their fracture toughness. A weak fiber/matrix interface allows the toughening mechanisms such as fiber bridging, crack

deflection, matrix microcracking, fiber debonding, and fiber pullout to be combined to reduce residual stresses and eliminate catastrophic failures. The methodology is based on micromechanics models in which customarily a representative volume element or unit cell is arranged in a square array pattern. However, the present approach employs a unique multilevel substructuring : from laminate to ply, to subply and then to fiber (figs. 1 and 2). The fiber is substructured into several slices and the micromechanics equations are applied at the slice level. The laminate theory is used recursively to obtain the laminate level properties. This technique has several advantages - it can model partial interphase bond, provides more accurate damage tracking and shows greater detail in stress distribution at a high computational efficiency.

The objective of this report is to describe the methodology and shows its capabilities and versatility by demonstrating several example cases for a select composite material system. The computationally predicted results are compared with experimental data, where such data is available.

FIBER-SUBSTRUCTURING AND MICROMECHANICS

The primary objective of the composite micromechanics is to determine equivalent elastic properties of a composite material in terms of the elastic properties of the constituent materials. The fiber sub-structuring technique divides the customary unit cell or the representative volume element (RVE) into several slices. The micromechanics equations are developed at the slice level, i.e. the slice equivalent properties are computed based on the properties of the fiber, matrix and the interphase. The micromechanics equations are based on mechanics of materials approach and use certain simplifying assumptions. They are not mathematically rigorous in that, although they do ensure the force equilibrium in all directions, but they do not impose the continuity of displacements, strains and stresses across various constituents. Such a rigorous solution can only be obtained through the use of three-dimensional theory of elasticity. However, such a solution is quite tedious for composite materials. The micromechanics predictions are routinely compared with those of detailed three-dimensional finite element analyses and with measured data to ensure adequacy of mechanics formulation and inclusion of all physical phenomena. The micromechanics equations are not shown here because of page limitations, but are available elsewhere (ref. 1). The laminate theory equations are available in any standard textbook on composite mechanics such as ref. 2.

The fiber substructuring approach is general , versatile and applicable to any kind of composite material. By controlling the number of slices in a unit cell, one can easily incorporate various degrees of bond around the fiber circumference. The fiber breaks, matrix microcracking etc. can be easily modeled and their effects on the ply thermal and mechanical properties/response can be easily evaluated.

Figure 1.—Integrated analysis approach embedded in CEMCAN computer code.

Figure 2.—Ply/fiber substructuring concepts for ceramic matrix composites micromechanics.
 (a) Horizontal slicing (along 2-2 direction).
 (b) Vertical slicing (along 3-3 direction; note: 1-1 is along fiber direction).
 (c) Individual slice showing fiber, matrix, and interphase regions.

MATERIAL NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOR

The authors during their past research have developed a unified law to describe the material degradation behavior applicable to composite materials. The law referred to as multi-factor interaction relationship (MFIR) accounts for the degradation effects of environment, fabrication, and loads on the constituent material behavior. However, in the present work dealing with the ceramic matrix composites, the constituent properties, namely the modulus and the coefficient of thermal expansion, are considered a function of temperature only. As an example, the modulus is assumed to have the following functional relationship with the temperature:

$$\frac{E}{E_0} = \left(\frac{T_f - T}{T_f - T_0} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where E is the modulus at temperature T , E_0 is the reference modulus at temperature T_0 , and the T_f is the final temperature where the modulus is zero. Based on the available experimental data, the exponent n and the final temperature T_f must be calibrated separately for fiber and matrix materials.

MICROSTRESSES AND STRESS REDISTRIBUTION DUE TO PROGRESSIVE FRACTURE

The thermal and mechanical loads are specified or obtained at the laminate level. Through the successive use of lamination theory, the stresses and strains at the mid-plane of the slices are obtained. The constituent microstresses are then computed from microstress equations that relate the equivalent slice stress to the constituent stresses. These equations are also based on the principles of micromechanics.

Non-linearities in the stress-strain behavior occur due to the dependence of constituent properties on temperature etc. (material non-linearity) as well as due to matrix microcracking that leads to stress redistribution. Both of these are accounted for in the present work. In the present work, the failure is based on maximum stress criterion. Once, the stress in a constituent exceeds the allowable value, that constituent is assumed to have failed and the corresponding modulus of that constituent is assigned an almost negligible value. A slice is assumed to have failed in the normal direction if the fiber portion of the slice indicated a stress value higher than the fiber fracture strength in the longitudinal direction. Similarly, a slice is assumed to have failed in the transverse direction if the matrix region stresses indicate failure in the transverse normal or shear direction. Once, a slice fails, all the stresses that are carried by that slice up to that point are redistributed to the regions that have not failed. The load that was carried by that slice is added to the laminate load and a laminate analysis is carried out again (fig. 3). This process is continued for a given load step until an equilibrium (convergence) is reached between the applied load and a damage state. Presently, the convergence is checked for laminate mid-plane strains, ply and slice strains. When all the strains are within 5 percent of the values from the previous iteration, convergence is assumed to have been reached. This mechanism is mainly responsible for the overall non-linear behavior in the laminate stress-strain curve at the room temperature.

Figure 3.—Local stress redistribution due to progressive fracture. Failure based on maximum stress criterion.

Figure 4.—Effect of temperature on constituent (fiber and matrix) moduli according to equation (1), $(E/E_0) = [(T_f - T)/(T_f - T_0)]^n$. Final fiber temperature, T_f , 2500 °C for $n = 0.25$; final matrix temperature, T_f , 2200 °C for $n = 0.1$.

Figure 5.—Room-temperature stress-strain curves to failure of [0]₈ and [90]₈ SiC/RBSN composite.

The associated micromechanics equations, fiber sub-structuring technique and macromechanics/laminate theory equations are programmed into a computer code - CEMCAN (Ceramic Matrix Composites Analyzer, ref. 3). A resident databank of constituent properties of commonly available materials is also included in the computer program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the methodology and its capabilities, a SiC/RBSN composite system (SCS-6 fibers in a reaction bonded silicon nitride matrix) was chosen because of vast amount of readily available experimental data. These data are documented in ref. 4, which forms the basis for the computed properties that are used in the present work. The use of such a calibration procedure is mandatory for any new material system in order to arrive at a set of constituent properties.

Prediction of Mechanical Properties

The interphase (usually a combination of outer carbon layer and the “reaction zone”) is treated as a separate constituent, the properties of which are not explicitly and readily available. Since the interphase modulus has little effect on longitudinal modulus of the unidirectional composite, fiber volume ratio (fvr) of the composite is calibrated from the measured longitudinal modulus of the unidirectional SiC/RBSN composite. Once, the nominal fvr is known, the interphase modulus is computed by comparing the measured and predicted values of the in-plane transverse modulus of the unidirectional composite. These values are shown in Table I. Once calibrated, these values are used to predict certain mechanical properties of a cross-ply and an angle-ply laminate and compared with measured values as shown in Tables II and III. The comparison is very good within the scatter of the measured values. To account for this scatter, one has to systematically account for the variabilities in various material and fabrication properties and perform a probabilistic micro- and macromechanics analysis. Such a analysis, predicts the mean value and a scatter bound on predicted values. Such an effort is well underway by the authors.

Prediction of Tensile Stress/Strain Behavior Under Uniaxial Loading

This section presents comparisons of experimental data and the predictions of composite stress/strain behavior under uniaxial tensile loading at room-temperature for various layups. The fabrication induced thermal residual stresses are accounted for in these simulations, i.e. composites are cooled down to room-temperature from an assumed stress-free temperature (little less than the actual fabrication temperature), prior to application of any mechanical loading. The material non-linearity as a function of temperature is accounted for in a form shown by equation 1 (fig. 4). The stress-strain curves for $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ composites are shown in figure 5. Based on the observed tensile strengths of these composites, the matrix in-situ tensile strength was calibrated to be 100 MPa (14.5 ksi) by comparing the knee in the stress-strain curve for $[0]_8$ composite and the average fiber bundle strength to be 2 GPa (285 ksi) by comparing the ultimate tensile strength of the same composite. The knee represents the initiation and subsequent saturation of matrix microcracking. These value agree well with the fiber and matrix tensile strengths reported in ref. 4. Once calibrated, the same strength values were used in subsequent simulations. The stress strain behavior of $[0]_8$ composite is a bi-

linear behavior, the knee of which represents matrix microcracking to saturation. During the second part of that curve, the load is entirely carried by the fibers only until fibers fracture. The behavior of $[90]_8$ laminate is linear until failure, at which point the matrix failed in transverse tension at a relatively low stress level of 45 MPa (6.5 ksi).

In contrast, the off-axis laminates $[10]_8$ and $[45]_8$ stress-strain behavior is largely linear up to failure as shown in figure 6. Such behavior is characteristic of a brittle failure. The final fracture in these laminates is controlled by a combination of matrix and interphase normal and shear failure modes. The room-temperature stress-strain curve to failure for a $[\pm 45]_8$ laminate is shown in figure 7. The shear strength of the matrix is estimated to be half the matrix tensile strength to match the ultimate tensile strength of these laminates. This laminate also fails in a combination of matrix normal and shear failure modes and shows a graceful failure. Although, the optical micrographs in ref. 4 confirmed the aforementioned failure modes, the unloading portion of the stress-strain curve for the laminate was not predicted. The experimental data shown in these figures was also taken from ref. 4.

TABLE I.—FIBER, MATRIX, AND CALIBRATED INTERPHASE PROPERTIES OF SiC/RBSN COMPOSITE SYSTEM

Constituent	Property								
	Poisson's ratio, ν	Modulus, E		Shear modulus, G		Coefficient of thermal expansion, α		Thermal conductivity, K	
		GPa	Mpsi	GPa	Mpsi	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{F}$	W/m-K	Btu/ft-hr- $^{\circ}\text{F}$
SiC (SCS-6) Fiber	0.17	390	56.6	117	17	4.1	2.3	22	12.7
RBSN Matrix	.22	110	15.95	45	6.5	2.2	1.2	5	2.9
Interphase	.22	3.5	.5	1.4	.2	2.0	1.1	2.0	1.2

TABLE II.—PREDICTED (CEMCAN) AND MEASURED ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF SiC/RBSN $[0]_8$ LAMINATE

[Unidirectional SiC/RBSN $[0]_8$ composite fiber volume ratio, 0.36^a]

Value	Property						
	Young's modulus (longitudinal), E_{11}		Young's modulus (transverse), E_{22}		In-plane shear modulus, G_{12}		Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}
	GPa	Mpsi	GPa	Mpsi	GPa	Mpsi	
Predicted	189	27.4	68.3	9.9	27	3.9	0.21
Measured ^b	193±7	28±1	69±3	10±0.4	31±3	4.5±0.4	.2

^aThe measured value of longitudinal modulus E_{11} for a unidirectional composite was used to compute fiber volume ratio (fvr) whereas the transverse modulus E_{22} was used to compute the interphase modulus.

^bReference 4

TABLE III.—PREDICTED (CEMCAN) AND MEASURED ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF SiC/RBSN $[0_2/90_2]_8$ and $[\pm 45_2]_8$ LAMINATES

Laminate	Property						
	Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	Young's modulus (longitudinal), E_{11}		Young's modulus (transverse), E_{22}		In-plane shear modulus, G_{12}	
		GPa	Mpsi	GPa	Mpsi	GPa	Mpsi
$[0_2/90_2]_8$	0.112	129	18.7	129	18.7	27	3.9
Predicted	.12	124±6	18±0.9	124±6	18±0.9	31±2	4.5±0.3
Measured ^a							
$[\pm 45_2]_8$	0.46	78.6	11.4	78.6	11.4	58	8.4
Predicted	.36	78±3	11.3±0.4	78±3	11.3±0.4	---	---
Measured ^a							

^aReference 4

Influence of Partial Interphase Bond

The concept of fiber substructuring allows one to specify a partial bond around the fiber circumference and integrate its effect up to the composite properties and response. The variation of some composite mechanical and thermal properties as a function of fiber circumference debonded is shown in figure 8. Longitudinal or fiber-controlled properties show little degradation whereas the transverse properties reveal greater degradation as a function of debonding. The properties plotted have been normalized with respect to the property for a composite with no debonding.

Figure 6.—Room-temperature stress-strain curves to failure of [10]₈ and [45]₈ laminates of SiC/RBSN.

Figure 7.—Room-temperature stress-strain curves to failure of [±45]_{2s} SiC/RBSN laminate.

Figure 8.—Variation of thermal and mechanical properties (normalized with respect to property with strong interphase) due to partial bonding.

CONCLUSIONS

A unique and novel fiber sub-structuring technique has been presented here. Although, general in nature, the technique is especially well-suited for the simulation of ceramic matrix composites behavior. Its features are illustrated with select examples. Experimental validation is provided where such data is available. This concept enables one to study in greater local detail ceramic matrix composites behavior pertaining to varying degree of interfacial bond. The matrix microcracking at relatively low stress levels and the resulting redistribution of stress is also taken into account. Based on the results shown for the SiC/RBSN composite system, the following specific conclusions can be drawn:

1. Fiber substructuring captures and represents greater local detail than other unit-cell based micromechanics theories.
2. The predictions from the simulations have been successfully verified for this particular composite system for available data.
3. The material non-linear behavior model and stress redistribution with progressive damage have enabled the prediction of stress-strain behavior up to failure. The agreement with experimentally observed behavior is excellent for this particular composite system.

REFERENCES

1. Murthy, P.L.N. and Chamis, C.C. : Towards the Development of Micromechanics Equations for Ceramic Matrix Composites via Fiber Substructuring. NASA TM-105246, 1992.
2. Agarwal, B.D. and Broutman, L.J.: Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites. Second Ed., Wiley and Sons, New York, 1990.
3. Mital, S.K. and Murthy, P.L.N. : CEMCAN - Ceramic Matrix Composites Analyzer User's Guide - Version 2.0 NASA TM-107187, 1996.
4. Bhatt R.T. and Phillips, R.E. : Laminate Behavior of SiC Fiber-Reinforced Reaction-Bonded Silicon Nitride Matrix Composites. NASA TM-101350, 1988.